

swissuniversities

swissuniversities
Effingerstrasse 15, Postfach
3001 Bern
www.swissuniversities.ch

**Programme Open Science II
Action Line B5.2 ORD Specialists / Data Stewardship
Application Form Extension of Action Plan**

Please fill in the present application form if you want to **submit a project application for a higher education institution that has already implemented a B5.2 project and that would like to expand their existing plan according to the current implementation status.**

Important: Applications will only be considered if they submitted an expression of interest by 24 January 2025 (please refer to the [Application Guidelines](#) for detailed information).

The application form must be submitted, together with the necessary attachments, at the following address **by 17 February 2025**: open-science@swissuniversities.ch
The subject line of the e-mail must contain the following: "Action line B5.2" and the short title of the project.

Content of the application:

- 1) The present application form (as PDF **and** Word)
- 2) The [budget form for individual projects](#) or [budget form for cooperation projects](#) (as Excel)

1. General information

Full project title

Advancement of the Data Stewardship Programm and Research Data Management Support at the University of Basel

Short title of the project (max. 20 characters)

Data Stewardship Universität Basel

Participating institution(s)

1 Applicant / Lead institution	Universität Basel
2 Partner institution:	Click here to enter text
3 Partner institution:	Click here to enter text
4 Partner institution:	Click here to enter text
N Further partner institutions:	Click here to enter text

Federal contribution applied for (total)

CHF 54'532.53

Breakdown of the requested federal contribution per participating institution

Please refer to the Guidelines for the PgB programmes managed by swissuniversities ([German](#) | [French](#) | [English](#)) for financing terms and conditions.

CHF 54'532.53 for Universität Basel

CHF [Click here to enter text](#) for [Click here to enter text](#)

CHF [Click here to enter text](#) for [Click here to enter text](#)

CHF [Click here to enter text](#) for [Click here to enter text](#)

CHF [Click here to enter text](#) for [Click here to enter text](#)

Total project budget (incl. matching funds)

CHF 109'065.06

Start and end date of the project

Start date of the project: 01 July 2025 (01.04.2025 at the earliest)

End date of the project: 30 June 2025 (31.07.2026 at the latest)

Brief description of the project (max. 250 words)

Please note: In the event of funding, this summary will be published on the swissuniversities homepage.

The support for research data management and the data stewardship program have been successfully established at the University of Basel. The activities of the data stewardship coordination and the data stewards during the initial project and the first funding phase of swissuniversities have increased the overall awareness of research data management and the recognition of good research data management as a crucial element of research integrity and transparency, but also of data and information security in the context of research. With the planned introduction of a data classification at the University of Basel, additional support is needed to ensure the necessary changes in established research data management processes. Targeted, low-threshold support for researchers in making these changes is crucial. This should include general guidance and support, subject- and domain-specific advice, and the establishment of efficient and secure workflows together with research groups and departments. Our goal is to provide this support to researchers through the data stewards already working at the University of Basel. Together with three research groups from different disciplines, the data stewards will develop use cases for research data management in the context of data classifications, which will then be adapted for other departments with the involvement of all data stewards. In addition, an overview of sensitive data and frequently used tools will be developed based on existing data sources, which can be used to reliably improve services and infrastructures for research data management. On this basis, the training program can then be adapted for different target groups and new teaching formats can be created. Overall, linking the implementation of data classification with reassessing the maturity of Research Data Management routines and respective support services, will foster the professionalization of Research Data Management at the University of Basel.

Project Leader

Name:

Silke Bellanger

swissuniversities

Academic title:	M.A.
Function:	Head of Digital Services and Open Science
Institution:	UB Basel, Universität Basel
Address:	Schönbeinstrasse 18-20
ZIP code, city:	4056 Basel
Phone:	+41 61 207 56 69
E-Mail:	silke.bellanger@unibas.ch

2. Extending an existing action plan

The projects and action plans that were implemented from 2023–2024 are based on the narrow definition of data stewardship and therefore focused on the employment of data stewards. From 2025, the call will be extended to include other people who take on ORD and data stewardship tasks at the higher education institutions (cf. the [Application Guidelines](#)). Based on their 2022 action plans, eligible higher education institutions can submit a project application for a corresponding broadening of their activities and measures.

swissuniversities

To apply for this call, you must submit this completed application form, together with the relevant budget form, by 17 February 2025 at the following address:

open-science@swissuniversities.ch

Please summarise your action plan and describe the current status of implementation (max. 500 words)

The University of Basel successfully implements its Data Steward Program under the Open Science - Phase B project, improving research data management across all seven faculties through a series of work packages. The project will end on 30.6.2025, the additional 6 months will be used to set up the new overall governance of the Research Data Management Support Network.

Thanks to the funding from swissuniversities, two additional Data Stewardship Coordinators could be hired temporary and another Data Stewardship Coordinator position within the Open Science Team of the University Library could be made permanent ahead of schedule and will help maintain program continuity and support future RDM initiatives. These roles have been critical to improving project operations and facilitating program initiatives.

The onboarding of new data stewards was successfully completed, with 37 data stewards appointed across all faculties and affiliated institutes, ensuring comprehensive coverage and effective integration of all relevant research areas. A comprehensive train-the-trainer program was implemented, offering several courses over two years. Data stewards received certificates for each course, and additional events were held to update them on RDM developments and to foster knowledge sharing within the network.

The governance structures of the existing Research Data Management Network were evaluated and improved based on feedback from data stewards and RDM experts. Key improvements included the establishment of a Strategy Group, clarification of the role of the data stewardship coordinators, standardization of support request processes, refinement of data steward roles, and implementation of a centralized activity reporting system. Internal and external communication channels remain effective, and as an efficient working method for all network members, intensive collaboration sprints were successfully established and will continue beyond the project. In addition, job description templates were developed to formalize data steward roles.

The project identified and prioritized key research data management needs, such as developing a checklist for handling personal data, gathering requirements for collaboration tools for sensitive data, and documenting data retention and deletion processes. Initial sprints resulted in published checklists and

reports, with further work planned beyond the project timeline to ensure comprehensive coverage of complex issues. This will be one of the starting points for the next funding period.

Several roadshows were conducted to increase the visibility of RDM services and data stewards across the University. These events ranged from short presentations at meetings to larger information sessions such as the Clinical Research Day.

Developing domain-specific best practices for RDM across all faculties was challenging due to varying capacities of data stewards and differing priorities within faculties. Pilot projects were initiated in selected departments, such as Biomedicine and Psychology, resulting in checklists and recommendations. Ongoing efforts include documenting best practices in a central wiki and contributing to the revision of the University's Integrity Policy to support RDM across all research units. This will be another starting point for the next funding period. Collaboration with doctoral program coordinators led to the development and piloting of discipline-specific RDM training courses for doctoral students. These courses received positive feedback and established ongoing collaborations to embed RDM in doctoral training and increase awareness and use of RDM services among doctoral students. Train-the-trainer-courses and trainings for researchers will be adapted in the next funding period.

Describe the newly set goals for 2025–2026, taking into account the broadening of the activities in the field of data stewardship (max. 500 words)

During the upcoming funding period, the goal of embedding research data management into everyday research routines and institutionalizing research data management support within the university organization will be advanced by focusing on the implementation of the data classification at the University of Basel and its effective challenges and opportunities for research data management.

The introduction of data classification, which requires explicit differentiation between different data protection needs, implies that additional support is needed to ensure that the necessary changes in established research data management processes can be successfully implemented by researchers. Targeted, low-threshold support for researchers in making these changes is crucial. This should include general guidance and support, subject- and domain-specific advice, and the establishment of efficient and secure workflows in collaboration with research groups and departments. Closely monitored implementation can promote acceptance of data classification.

In addition, the introduction of the data classification offers opportunities for the ongoing professionalization of research data management. It can promote a deliberate and reflective approach to research data management at all stages of the research data cycle, and in particular help to address and overcome difficulties in:

- Transitions between active research and the end of projects (data curation, storage, data publication, licensing, reuse, on- and off-boarding of research

staff)

- Transitions between different phases of a researcher's career (sensitive data, data reuse, data ownership, roles and responsibilities)
- Research data management in multi-institutional and international collaborations (agreements, contracts, shared technologies, access management).

swissuniversities

It is an opportunity to

- Assess the maturity of domain-specific research data management routines and enable up-scaling of skills where needed
- Encourage peer-to-peer exchange of best practices and efficient solutions, in particular with regard to data protection and sharing.
- Provide an overview of the types and volumes of data being worked with at the university, thereby increasing the recognition of their value as a research activity.
- Promote the potential of data publication when data does not need to be protected
- Better understand the common needs of research groups in terms of instrumentation and tools, data classes, and how to tailor RDM services accordingly.

The overall goal of combining the implementation of data classification and the reassessment of existing research data management practices is to increase the maturity and quality of RDM services at the University of Basel in terms of skilled handling of sensitive data and increased data sharing and publication of non-sensitive data.

And although the organization of RDM support at the University of Basel has always involved different service providers and thus different data-related professions, the upcoming project will further strengthen the collaboration between data stewards, data protection, information security, and data managers and data scientists affiliated with the IT- and core facilities.

Please list the new measures planned for 2025–2026 to achieve the objectives you set out (max. 500 words)

The first step in adapting research data management to the requirements of data classification will be to develop use cases with three data stewards in their respective institutes and research groups that have already agreed to participate (Pharmaceutical Studies, Biomedical Ethics, Nursing Studies). The development of the use cases will involve organizing workshops with the research groups, conducting information sessions on the new data classification, and meticulously documenting and analyzing typical research processes and data lifecycles in the respective domain. In addition, we will work with data stewards to identify commonly used tools, characterize datasets, and evaluate existing prac-

tices against the new classifications. The results will include the creation of tailored guidelines and workflows, reviewing the results with other researchers in the domain, and facilitating their adaptation of the guidelines and workflows. The next step will focus on generalizing the findings from the domain-specific use cases to broader applications. This will include re-evaluating the existing research data management best practices for psychology, biomedicine, and bio-engineering that were developed during the last funding period. The RDM team will draft transferable guidelines and workflows, subject them to review by all data stewards, and organize peer-to-peer discussions among researchers to foster cross-disciplinary learning. In addition, this work package will synchronize these efforts with the overall infrastructure development related to data classification and reassess the University's RDM policy (2020).

In order to understand the challenges and opportunities presented by the implementation of data classification, another critical component is the comprehensive mapping of data sets across the University of Basel. This task involves aggregating information from various data sources, analyzing the collected metadata, and communicating the results to relevant stakeholders, in particular the IT and high computing facilities involved in building secure infrastructures for working with sensitive data. A side effect will be to assess which non-sensitive data sets can be openly shared and recognized as research results. Data publication guidelines will be revised accordingly.

In parallel to these efforts, the project will focus on adapting RDM training to accommodate researchers at all levels of qualification. This will involve re-engaging with graduate school coordinators, updating training content, integrating new formats such as video tutorials, and incorporating results from the above steps into training materials.

Overall, the University Library's RDM project represents a strategic effort to improve data management practices, foster interdisciplinary collaboration, and ensure that researchers in all disciplines have the resources and support they need to manage their data responsibly and efficiently. Through careful planning, targeted use cases, and ongoing knowledge transfer, the project aims to establish a robust RDM framework that aligns with the University's research goals and data and information security requirements.

Describe your overall work plan for the implementation of the project (max. 500 words)

Work Package 1: Project Coordination / RDM Network Coordination

Tasks: Implementation and monitoring of the new work packages, coordination with all relevant partners of the RDM network and stakeholders at the university; management of the network and the data stewards; ensuring reporting to the relevant bodies of the RDM governance.

Milestones: 1.) All deliverables defined; 3.) Project planning and scheduling of new actions completed; 3.) Project completed.

Responsible: RDM Team University Library (Data Stewardship Coordinators)

Work Package 2: Pharmaceutical Studies Use Case

Tasks: Set up workshops with the selected research group in pharmaceutical studies, organize information events on the new data classification, document and analyze their typical steps in active research as well as in all phases of the research data lifecycle, list the commonly used tools and characterize the datasets, evaluate the existing practices together with the research group in light of the data classification, draft guidelines and workflows, present the results to other research groups within the department and ensure that they are able to adapt them for their research group.

Milestones: 1.) At least one workshop has taken place 2.) Guidelines have been finalized 3.) Presentation to colleagues in the department has taken place.

Responsible: RDM Team University Library (Data Stewardship Coordinators), Data Steward Pharmaceutical Studies; probably in collaboration with Data Protection Office, Chief Information Officer, High Computing Facility (sciCORE).

Work Package 3: Biomedical Ethics Use Case

analogous to WP 2

Work Package 4: Use Case Nursing Studies

analogous to WP 2

Work Package 5: Generalization and knowledge transfer of the domain-specific use cases

Task: Re-evaluate existing best practices for psychology, biomedicine and bioengineering; analyze the results of WP 2-4 with respect to different data types and classes; draft transferable guidelines and workflows; review by all data stewards; organize peer-to-peer discussion among researchers; synchronize with the overall infrastructure development as part of the introduction of data classification; re-evaluate and edit the university policy on research data management.

Milestones: 1.) Workshop with data stewards; 2.) At least one peer-to-peer event in another area; 3.) Updated RDM policy.

Responsible: RDM team University Library (Data Stewardship Coordinators), all Data Stewards; probably in collaboration with Data Protection Office, Chief Information Officer, High Computing Facility (sciCORE), VR Research.

Work Package 6: Datasets @University of Basel

Tasks: survey of datasets at the University of Basel; aggregation of information on datasets registered in different data sources; analysis; information to relevant stakeholders.

Milestones: 1.) survey has been sent; 2.) overview on data sets has been made; 3.) results have been communicated

Responsible: Responsible: RDM Team University Library (Data Stewardship Coordinators), all Data Stewards; probably in collaboration with Data Protection Office, Chief Information Officer, High Computing Facility (sciCORE) and IT-S.

Work Package 7: Adaptation of RDM training for researchers at all qualification levels

Tasks: re-establish contact with all graduate school coordinators; update and adapt content and integrate new formats such as videos for training for different target groups; integrate results from other work packages into the training materials.

Milestones: 1.) New training materials will be designed 2.) New training has been delivered

Responsible: RDM team University Library (Data Stewardship Coordinators),
Data Stewards

If desired, insert a graphical representation of your work plan here (e.g. in the form of a Gantt chart):

swissuniversities

Please describe the strategic and financial sustainability of the measures and their further implementation after 2026 (max. 250 words)

As stated in the proposal for the previous funding period, the introduction of data stewards and the institutionalization of the RDM network are strategic decisions of the Rectorate; within the framework of its strategy 2022-2030, the University of Basel has set itself the general goal of strengthening future-oriented research areas in connection with the digital transformation and ensuring access to research-relevant data. The research data and results of the University of Basel are to be made publicly available as far as ethically and legally possible in accordance with international standards.

With the institutionalization of the network, support for research data management in Basel has been organized from the outset in a model that exploits synergies through collaboration between the various service providers. In this way, the services, expertise, skills and infrastructures of the different service units can be used efficiently to support the different phases of the research data cycle. The establishment of data stewards in existing research-related services supports this approach. The interaction between data stewards and the network promotes the reuse of services, knowledge and skills, or the development of these in tandem.

The overall goal of the University of Basel remains to integrate and promote research data management support as optimally and comprehensively as possible into existing organizational structures. Nevertheless, the project will examine measures that can further support the work of the data stewardships.

How does the project promote gender, cultural, and age diversity within its team and among its beneficiaries? How does it – at different stages of the academic career – address researchers' needs and ensure relevance? (max. 250 words)

The RDM network, including the 37 data stewards, is currently diverse in a number of ways. Members have different cultural backgrounds, come from different language regions, cover a wide range of different academic qualification groups and subject areas, and are of different ages and genders.

The Data Stewardship Coordination within the University Library's Open Science Team relies on inclusivity and recognition of diversity to manage the network. It follows the Code of Conduct of the University of Basel. The University of Basel is committed to a culture of dialog and to the values of integrity, respect, openness, equality and inclusion. Discrimination, bullying and sexual harassment will not be tolerated (<https://www.unibas.ch/en/University/Administration-Services/Vice-President-s-Office-for-People-and-Culture/Personal-Integrity/Code-of-Conduct.html>).

The support services provided by the RDM Network are explicitly aimed at researchers at all levels of qualification, with a particular focus on the career needs of PhD students and postdocs. The recognition of disciplinary diversity and differences in research cultures is a core understanding of all services provided.

3. Project Budget

Please select one of the Excel forms and attach it to your application:

- [Budget form for individual projects](#) **or**
- [Budget form for cooperation projects](#) in case of a cooperation project

swissuniversities

Federal contribution

Project funds must be used by the end date of the project. Any unused balance must be returned to SERI.

Own contribution

Eligible higher education institutions must provide at least 50% of own institutional contributions for the entire duration of the project. Own contributions may take the form of financial and in-kind contributions. The own (financial) contribution in real money must be at least 50% of the federal contribution.

Please refer to Guidelines for the 2025–2026 PgB programmes managed by swissuniversities for more detailed information ([German](#) | [French](#) | [English](#)).